

VIRTUAL TESTING OF RECYCLED GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER SANDWICH CORES

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ABSTRACT

End of life strategies for wind turbine blades become increasingly important, as an ever-growing number of wind turbines reaches its decommissioning date. Various types of recycling i. e. mechanical, thermal and chemical, are currently the subject of research.

The goal of this study is, to assess the suitability of recycled glass fibre reinforced polymers (rGFRP) from wind turbine blade as a raw material for truck trailer floor panels. In order to achieve weight-wise competitive material properties with the currently used plywood, rGFRP is used in a sandwich part, as both skin and core material. A static simulation and a linear buckling analysis of established and rare core types have been conducted to compare these options regarding stiffness, mechanical stresses and susceptibility for buckling. Compared to the currently used plywood, rGFRP sandwich parts show significantly higher stiffness. However, stresses exceeding the tensile strength of rGFRP in the skins occur, highlighting the need to either further improve the recycled material or to add virgin GFRP. Equally high stresses in the core have to be investigated further, as stress concentrations occur on sharp edges and corners in the core geometries. Preliminary analysis of buckling behaviour indicates that buckling is not an issue for the used wall thickness at the expected loads.

1. INTRODUCTION

Wind turbines are essential for producing clean and renewable energy. With the rapid growth of the wind energy industry, the extensive use of composite materials in wind turbine blades is posing significant environmental challenges [1]. To fulfill the design criteria of durability and high strength to weight ratio, wind turbine blades are manufactured from non-biodegradable materials such as glass fibers and thermoset polymers like epoxy resin. An exceeding number of turbines reach their end-of-life, necessitating the need for comprehensive recycling and reuse strategies. As of right now, wind turbine blades at their end of life are either burnt or stored at landfills [2]. These strategies however, lead to a waste of resources and could also be legally prohibited in the future. For example, WindEurope, a leading non-profit association that represents and promotes the wind energy industry across Europe, proposed a landfill ban for wind turbine blades in Europe from 2025 onwards [3]. Of the currently known recycling methods [4], mechanical recycling is still the only economically and ecologically sensible process according to literature [5].

The goal of this study is to evaluate the suitability of mechanically recycled glass fiber reinforced polymer (rGFRP) as a raw material for truck trailer floor panels. Plywood, with a density of 680 kg/m³, is currently used in truck trailer floors. With a density of more than 1500 kg/m³ and similar tensile strength as plywood, the use of rGFRP only makes sense if used as a sandwich part. To determine the ideal core geometry, different core geometries were virtually tested regarding the stresses that occur and their sensitivity towards buckling using Finite Element Analysis.

2. MATERIAL

The starting point for this study was unsorted shredded wind turbine blade material. Besides glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP), this material contained metals such as copper (likely from lightning rod) and lead (likely from balancing weights) among other things. While no lead was found after further refinement, the copper could only be partially removed by the available metal separator using eddy currents.

Plates of shredded material mixed with virgin epoxy resin were manufactured by a press process, curing the material at 80 °C for 90 minutes. Density was measured using the immersion method according to ISO 1183-1:2019. To determine E1 and E2 for rGFRP, uniaxial tensile tests in accordance with ISO 527-4 were carried out. The Poisson ratio was measured by applying strain gauges. Samples with a size of 100 x 10 mm were cut out in 0°, 45° and 90° to the length axis of the panel. These angles are not corresponding to any fibre direction. No significant difference was found, which is why isotropic in-plane behaviour was assumed. Tests in thickness direction were not carried out and isotropic behaviour was assumed. A simulation was carried out to estimate the effect of that assumption.

Three different grain sizes were investigated (0-0.355 mm, 0.355-1.4 mm, 1.4 mm-2.8 mm). The middle fraction (0.355-1.4 mm) showed a slightly weaker mechanical performance in bending and tensile tests than the finest grain size but was available in a larger quantity and therefore selected for further steps in the project. Different epoxy resins were investigated of which KR 44.39 showed the best performance in tensile tests. The weight percentage of the shredded material is approximately 60%, resulting in a fibre volume ratio of approximately 30%.

A comparison between the values of rGFRP and the currently used plywood are given in Table 1. The values for plywood are from the “Finnish plywood-27 mm birch” entry in the Altair ESA-Comp database.

Table 1 Important mechanical quantities of rGFRP and plywood

Property		rGFRP	Plywood
E_1	[GPa]	10.03±0.4	7.67
E_2	[GPa]	10.03±0.4	7.21
E_3	[GPa]	10.03±0.4	3
σ_{1t}	[MPa]	53.1±3.3	38.7
σ_{2t}	[MPa]	53.1±3.3	36.3
ν_{12}	–	0.3	0.05
ρ	[kg/m ³]	1540±10	680

rGFRP is the raw material for both, the skins and the core.

3. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND DESIGN CONSTRAINTS

The planned application for the material is as floor panel in a truck trailer. The truck trailer substructure consists of a steel frame (*Figure 1*) and floor panels screwed onto the steel frame. The largest unsupported span of a panel in the truck trailer has dimensions of 1600 mm x 500 mm. The total height of the floor panels is limited to 28 mm.

Figure 1 Schematic top view of truck trailer steel frame segment: steel beams (black lines) and panels (white spaces in between), of which the largest unsupported span is highlighted in red

The critical load case is a forklift with a weight of 3600 kg per wheel standing at the weakest point, which is usually the center of the panel, for 5 minutes. The contact area of a wheel based on dimensioning guidelines for plywood panels is 180 x 80 mm. The load applied on the contact area amounts to a pressure of 2.45 MPa.

From a manufacturing perspective, project partners agreed to focus predominantly on core patterns that are easy to manufacture while using a pressing process.

The grain size of the shredded material of 1.4 mm determines the theoretical lower limit for the thickness of a pressed structure.

The weight of the sandwich panel should be equal to or less than the weight of the plywood panel. Furthermore, the stiffness of the panel should be equal to or higher than the stiffness of the plywood panel.

4. INVESTIGATED CORE TYPES

In the current analysis, sandwich parts consisting of 4 mm thick skins and a core with a height of 20 mm have been investigated. The only factor, that has been varied was the core geometry.

The investigated core types can be divided into four groups: Corrugated, honeycombs, Miura-ori foldcore geometries and generalized Resch pattern foldcore geometries. Corrugated and honeycombs are well-established core types. Honeycombs are difficult to manufacture using a pressing process due to their vertical elements. They were nevertheless included as benchmark, as literature indicates great bending, compression and shear properties [8]–[10]. Miura-ori cores and cores inspired by generalized Resch pattern geometries represent rare core types but have also been investigated in the literature [11], [12]. For an overview of all investigated core geometries, see Table 2.

A wall thickness of 2 mm was chosen for all geometries. Dimensions of the cores were chosen so that the volume filling degree was between 18-22%. By that, equivalent weight with the plywood panel was achieved.

5. SIMULATION SETUP

For virtual testing, a geometrically non-linear static simulation and a linear buckling analysis (LBA) were set up using the Finite Element software Abaqus CAE 2020. The goal of the static simulation was to determine the stresses and displacements in skins and core when the forklift stands in the center of the panel. Therefore, a load of 2.45 MPa (see Section 3) was used. A static simulation of the plywood panel was carried out for comparison. In the LBA, an initial value of 1 was used, which is common in literature. The analysis then solves for eigenvalues which will give you the factor by which the initial load has to be multiplied to reach the buckling loads. In either case, the load was distributed evenly over the entire contact area. For the static simulations, a symmetry condition was used, allowing to calculate only half of the geometry. For the buckling simulations, the entire model had to be calculated.

As core cell dimensions (i. e. 20 mm square honeycomb cell length) are in the same order of magnitude as the overall sandwich thickness (28 mm), the cores were not homogenized but simulated as discrete structures, allowing a visualization of local effects to some extent.

Table 2 Investigated core geometries; length-direction is roughly horizontal and width direction roughly vertical

Core Type			
Corrugated	Triangular (C Tri)	Rectangular (C Rec)	Trapezoidal (C Trap)
Honeycombs	Square (H Square)	Rectangular (H Rec)	Hexagonal (H Hex)
Miura-ori	V longitudinal (M V L)	V transversal (M V T)	M longitudinal (M M)
Resch	Triangular (R Tri)	Quadrangular (R Quad)	Hexagonal (R Hex)

For both simulations, “Tie”-contacts, simulating perfect bonding, were defined between the core top and bottom surfaces and the respective skin surfaces. For the LBA, movement in z-direction was prohibited ($U_3 = 0$) on all 4 edges, modelling the rigid connection via screws onto the trailer. On one side, in plane-movement was additionally constrained ($U_1, U_2 = 0$). For the static simulation, the boundary condition of one edge with prohibited movement in z-direction was replaced by the symmetry condition ($U_2=UR!=UR3=0$).

For the skins, quadratic shell elements (S8R) and for the core quadratic solid elements (C3D20R for corrugated and honeycomb cores, C3D10 for Miura-ori and Resch cores) were used. A 2 mm mesh was specified for the load area for the skins, while a 5 mm mesh was used outside of the load area. For the core, this general criterion was used as well – however for all Miura-ori or Resch cores at least two elements were assigned over any dimension (thickness, width and length) in the load area. For corrugated and honeycomb cores, there are at least three elements.

Mesh convergence studies were carried out for each core geometry groups i. e. corrugated cores, honeycombs, etc. for both, the static simulation and the LBA.

6. RESULTS

6.1. Static simulation

6.1.1. Estimation of thickness property influence

A simulation of a H-Rec sandwich with E_1, E_2 of the rGFRP and 5 MPa for E_3 (approximately half of E_1, E_2) was set up to determine the effect of assumption of isotropic material behaviour. The other properties to describe the material behaviour ($G_{12} = 3.03$ GPa, $G_{13} = G_{23} = 2.5$ GPa, $\nu_{13} = \nu_{23} = 0.3$) were taken from the “7781 Glass Fabric / MGS418” entry in the Altair ESA-Comp database – a typical glass fibre fabric in epoxy matrix. The simulation showed a slight increase of 8.3% in displacement compared to isotropic properties, indicating that thickness properties only slightly influence the displacement results.

6.1.2. Displacement

Several plots were derived from the results of the static simulation. One of the key takeaways is that all investigated core geometries have a significantly smaller displacement (max. 13.7 mm) than the plywood panel (16.5 mm, Figure 2). With the exception of the corrugated rectangular core, a clear trend by core type can be established: Miura-ori cores and Resch pattern cores are less stiff under bending (11.5-11.8 mm). Corrugated and honeycomb cores have lower displacements (10.9-11.2 mm), with the lowest values experienced by the corrugated trapezoidal and the rectangular honeycomb cores.

Figure 2 Maximum displacement in static simulation of different core types as a function of volume filling degree

The lower displacement of the rectangular honeycomb compared to the square honeycomb can be explained by its tighter spaces between the beam elements in the width direction. This feature was specifically put in place to increase stiffness. When the length to width ratio exceeds factor of 2, stresses occur predominantly in width direction, as that direction is much stiffer. Therefore, stiffening in the width direction improves the stiffness more than stiffening in the length direction. This is also the reason why corrugated cores are as stiff as honeycomb cores in this example and Miura-ori and Resch pattern cores are less stiff.

6.1.3. Skin stresses

The maximum tension stresses in skins for the different core geometries can be seen in Figure 3. For this analysis, stress maxima at the edges where boundary conditions were applied, were ignored. Overall, skin stresses are quite similar for all cores. A similar trend as in Figure 2 can be seen: stiff cores lead to less stress in the skins. For all core geometries, the maximum stress exceeds the ultimate tensile strength of GFRP by a significant margin. Figure 3 could have also been plotted for compression stresses, which show a very similar trend to the tensile stresses.

Figure 3 Maximum tension in skins in static simulation of different core types as a function of volume filling degree

6.1.4. Core stresses

Core stresses were evaluated as well and were in the same order of magnitude as the skin stresses and higher (peak stresses between 90 MPa and 300 MPa). However, a sensible evaluation is challenging: While Mesh convergence studies converge for skin stresses and displacements, they linearly increase or even slightly diverge for core stresses due to stress concentrations on corners and edges (i. e. Figure 4, Figure 5).

Figure 4 Edge of load area of square honeycomb with 1 (a), 2 (b) and 4 elements (c) over the width resulting in 74,7 MPa, 80,3 MPa and 91,7 MPa peak stress respectively; d: scale for all three simulations

Figure 5 Stress concentrations in quadratic Resch pattern in load area (a, b) with the corresponding scale (c)

Further investigations will take place to accurately evaluate the core stresses.

6.2. LBA

By employing an LBA, a preliminary investigation of the buckling load for each core geometry has been established. None of the core geometries failed at loads less than twice the currently used static load (Figure 6).

Further investigation by using a non-linear buckling analysis would be necessary to accurately determine the exact buckling loads. However, given the magnitude of the normal skin and core stresses in the static simulation, focus will be placed on evaluating the core stresses and improving static performance.

Figure 6 LBA buckling stress of different core types as a function of volume filling degree

7. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

A geometrically non-linear static simulation and a linear buckling analysis (LBA) were set up for sandwich parts differing in employed core geometry (different corrugated cores, honeycomb cores, Miura-ori cores and generalized Resch pattern cores). To evaluate their suitability for truck trailer floor panels, the results of the static simulation were compared to the simulation of the currently used plywood floor panel. All investigated core geometries showed significantly increased stiffness than the plywood panel. For all geometries, the skin stresses exceeded 100 MPa. Given the tensile strength of

rGFRP of 55 MPa, additional reinforcement or the use of virgin GFRP as skins is needed. Stresses in the core were in the same magnitude as the stresses in the skins. They need to be further investigated as stress concentrations occur on edges and at corners in the load area (global-local submodelling techniques). As a possible alternative, rGFRP foam cores, consisting of epoxy resin, blowing agents and shredded blade material, will be investigated. The LBA indicates that no core geometry is susceptible to buckling.

All investigations have been carried out for the load case where the load is applied centrally onto the panel for maximum bending stress. However, shear stress is maximized with the load closer to the panel edge, decreasing the area where shear can be relieved. This load case has to be investigated as well to accurately determine the highest shear loads.

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